

TO‘XTASH JOYLARIDAGI AVTOMOBILLARNING ICHIDAGI
TEMPERATURASINI PRAGNOZLASH

I.S. Sodiqov¹, J.O‘. Axmatjonov²

¹Doktor, Professor, Toshkent davlat transport universiteti, Toshkent, O‘zbekiston

²Magistrant, Toshkent davlat transport universiteti, Toshkent, O‘zbekiston

Annotatsiya. Maqolada avtomobil to‘xtash joylarida hosil bo‘layotgan temperaturasi chet el tajribalarida aniqlangan. Yildan–yilga havo harorati oshib bormoqda shuningdek, yuqori haroratli yozgi davrda to‘xtash joylaridagi avtomobillarga quyoshdan kelayotgan nurlarni qay darajada avtomobilga ta’siri qonuniyatlarini tasvirlash. Chet el tadqiqotlari natijasida avtomobga ta’sir ko‘rsatish omillar shundan iboratki to‘xtash joylaridagi avtomobillarga yuqori darajada ta’sir o‘tkazayotgani aniqlangan, buning oqibatida avtomobil kabinasidagi yuqori temperatura oqibatida bolalar va uy hayvonlarini o‘limi kuzatilgan. Shuni inobatga olgan holda, kabina ichidagi temperaturani pasaytirish maqsad qilib olingan, avtomobil qismlariga ta’sirini kamaytirish uchun optimal varianti tanlab olish.

Kalit so‘zlar. Haroratning o'zgarishi, to'xtab turgan transport vositalari, Quyosh radiatsiyasi.

O‘tkazilgan tadqiqotning yangiligi shundan iboratki, O‘zbekiston sharoitida yozgi issiq temperaturada avtomobil kabinasiga yuqori darajaga ta’sir ko‘rsatishi o‘rganib chiqilgan. Jahon adabiyotlari tahliliga ko‘ra, ko‘pgina davlatlarda O‘zbekiston hududida kuzatiladigan darajada jazirama harorat mavjud emasligi, shuningdek temperaturani pasaytirish uchun turli xil usullardan foydalanib haroratni pasaytirish ko‘zda tutilgan. Shu maqsadda mazkur tadqiqot ishi dolzarb muammolardan biri xisoblanadi. Bundan tashqari, haroratga sezgir bo‘lgan mahsulotlar (masalan, tez yordam va veterinariya vositalaridagi dorilar) yuqori haroratga salbiy ta'sir ko'rsatishi mumkin. Kabinadagi havo haroratining ko'tarilishini hisoblash uchun dinamik model ishlab chiqilgan bo'lib, u faqat uchta

parametr, mavjud standart meteorologik stantsiyalar: havo harorati, global radiatsiya va shamol tezligi.[1]

O‘rganilgan usullar.

Kabinaning havo harorati Θ_{Air} dinamik model bilan hisoblanadi. Kabinaning shaffof elementlari Φ_t va shaffof bo'lmagan Φ_o elementlarining energiya oqimlarini va HVAC tizimi Φ_v ni hisobga olgan holda hisoblanadi. Kabinaning ichida yo'lovchi, hayvonlar yoki boshqa energiya chiqaradigan komponentlar Φ_I hisobga olinadi. 1-rasmda energiyaning umumiy oqimlar ko'rinishi berilgan. Avtomobil salonidagi havo haroratining o'zgarish tezligi Θ_{Air} issiqlik balansi bilan hisoblanadi.

$$cm \frac{d\Theta_{Air}}{dt} = \Phi_T + \Phi_O + \Phi_I + \Phi_V$$

havo massasi (m) va termal issiqlik sig'imi bilan (c). Odatda, issiqlik energiya balansi (namlik) inobatga olinmaydi chunki avtomobil ichida namlik havo kamligi sababli bug'lanish imkoni yo'q. Suv bug'lanish imkoni yo'q degan taxmin ostida qabul qilamiz, suv bug'ining bosimi tashqi va ichki holatida bir xil bo'ladi.

Ko'k Mazda 323 (model 1982) avtomobil quyosh pardasi tajribalarda qo'llaniladi. Yon, orqa va old oynalarning shakli va o'lchamlari ko'rsatiladi. Barcha yon oynalar oq shaffof shishadan yasalgan. Old va orqa oynalar ham oq shishadan yasalgan. Avtomobil quyosh pardasi old va orqa tomondan kumush folga bilan koplaydi. [1]

Natijalar va tahlillar

O'zbekiston hududida havo harorati mutadil bo'lganligi uchun o'rtacha havo haroratini inobatga olingan holda to'xtab turgan avtomobillar ichidagi harorati aniqland va natijalar qabul qilindi.

1-rasm Viloyatlar bo'yicha yozgi maksimal havo haroratining o'zgarishi.

Viloyatlar	Temperatura (°C)	Viloyatlar	Temperatura (°C)	Viloyatlar	Temperatura (°C)	Viloyatlar	Temperatura (°C)
Qoraqalpog'iston	45,4	Akbatul	44,3	Yangi kishlaq	42,1	Denov	43,2
Jaslik	45,9	Tamdi	44,8	Dagbit	41,8	Shurchi	44,3
Aktumsu	42	Ayakagitma	44,8	Samarqand	40,3	Oygaining	43,2
Muynak	44,2	Karakul	44	Shaxrisabz	43,1	Pishin	49,4
Qung'iro	44,5	Buxara	45,2	Mincukur	42,2	Chimgan	44,5
Chimbay	44	Mashiku-duk	44,7	Akrabat	46,1	Tashkent	42,5
Taxtakupirik	43,3	Nurata	42,4	Shirobad	44,2	Kamchik	40,3
Nukus	44,3	Navoi	42,2	Termiz	44,4	Dukant	44,4
Taxiatosh	43,2	Mubarak	44,9	Dustlik	42,4	Almalik	42

Xiva	4 4	Qushra bad	4 1,4	Jizza x	4 2	Chim kurgn	4 4,5
Urganch	4 2,2	Paysha nba	4 0,5	G'all aorol	4 1,4	Sirda ryo	4 2,6
Bazaubay	4 5,2	Karshi	4 4,5	Baxm al	3 6,5	Yangi yul	4 2,2
Kokaral	4 0	Kokan d	4 0	Qura g'ntepa	3 9,2	Pop	4 1,4
Dexkana- bad	4 1,1	Boz	4 1,1	Bulug 'nur	4 1,1	Nama ngan	4 0,3
Yangiyer	4 3	Fergan a	4 1,1	Tuya mun	4 3,2	Andij an	4 1
Bekabod	4 1,1	Sarika nda	3 5,3	Suqo q	3 6,2	Angr en	3 8,2

2-rasm Viloyatlar va Shaharlar bo'yicha yozgi sharoitlarda maksimal havo harorati.

Viloyatlar	Temperatura (°C)	Viloyatlar	Temperatura (°C)	Viloyatlar	Temperatura (°C)	Viloyatlar	Temperatura (°C)
Qoraqal pog'iston	6 3.89	Akb aytal	6 2.89	Yangi kishlaq	6 0.89	Deno v	6 1.89
Jaslik	6 3.89	Tam di	6 2.89	Dagbi t	5 9.89	Shur chi	6 2.89
Aktums uk	6 0.89	Aya kagitma	6 2.89	Sama rkand	5 8.89	Oyga ing	5 1.89
Muynak	6 2.89	Kara kul	6 2.89	Shaxr isabz	6 1.89	Piske n	5 7.89
Qung'ir ot	6 2.89	Buxa ra	6 3.89	Minc hukur	5 0.89	Chim gan	5 2.89
Chimba y	6 2.89	Mas hiku-duk	6 2.89	Akra bat	5 4.89	Tash kent	6 0.89
Taxtaku pirik	6 1.89	Nura ta	6 0.89	Shiro bad	6 2.89	Kam chik	4 8.89
Nukus	6 2.89	Navo i	6 0.89	Termi z	6 2.89	Duka nt	5 2.89
Taxiatos h	6 1.89	Mub arak	6 2.89	Dustli k	6 0.89	Alma lik	6 0.89
Xiva	6 2.89	Qus hrabad	5 9.89	Jizzax	6 0.89	Chim kurgan	6 2.89

Urganch	6 0.89	Pays hanba	5 8.89	G'alla orol	5 9.89	Sirda ryo	6 0.89
Bazauba y	6 3.89	Kars hi	6 2.89	Baxm al	5 4.89	Yang iyul	6 0.89
Kokaral	5 8.89	Kok and	5 8.89	Qura g'ntepa	5 7.89	Pop	5 9.89
Dexkan a-bad	5 9.89	Boz	5 9.89	Bulug 'nur	5 9.89	Nam angan	5 8.89
Yangiye r	6 1.89	Ferg ana	5 9.89	Tuya mun	6 1.89	Andi jan	5 9.89
Bekabo d	5 9.89	Sari kanda	5 3.89	Suqoq	5 4.89	Angr en	5 6.89

3-rasmda Avtomobil to'xtash joylarida to'xtab turgan avtomobilning ichidagi havo haroratlari (30 minut misolida,)

4-rasmda Avtomobil to'xtash joylarida to'xtab turgan avtomobilning ichidagi maksimal havo haroratlari (30 minut misolida) grafigi.

Xulosa va tavsiyalar.

Chet el tadqiqotlaridan shu narsa ko‘rinib to‘ribdiki kabinadagi harorat oshib ketish oqibatida kabina ichidagi bolalar va uy hayvonlari o‘lishi kuzatilgan. Shuningdek, avtomobil kabinasidagi haroratni pasaytirish usullari haqida ma’lumot.Uzbekiston hududida yozgi iyun oylarida avtomobillar kabinasi qizib kerishini oldini olish va shu usullardan foydalanib havfli o‘lim holatlarini oldini olish.Shu bilan birgalikda, yozgi vaqlarda eng maksimal harorat Nukusda va eng past harorat Toshkent shahrida, shuningdek to'xtab turgan avtomobil ichidagi

harorat ham oshib ketishini ko'rishimiz mumkin. Shuningdek, Biz quyosh nuridan saqlash uchun kerakli daraxt turlarini tanlash orqali kamaytirishga erishishimiz mumkin.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar.

1. I.R. Dadour, I. Almanjahie, N. D. Fowkes, G. Keady, K. Vijayan, Temperature variations in a parked car, *Forensic Science International* 207 (2011) 205-211.
2. O. Kaynakli, M. Kilic, An investigation of thermal comfort inside an automobile during the heating period, *Applied ergonomics* 36 (2005) 301-312.
3. M. O. Korukcu, M. Kilic, The usage of IR thermography for the temperature measurements inside an automobile cabin, *International communications in heat and mass transfer* 36 (2009) 872-877.
4. A. Mezrhab, M. Bouzidi, Computation of thermal comfort inside a passenger car compartment, *Applied Thermal*
Adiv, A., & Wang, W. (1987). *ON-Street Parking Meter Behaviour*. Virginia 22161: National Technical Information Service, Springfield.
Al Matawah, J., & Jadaan, K. (2013). Road User Attitudes towards Safety Initiatives in Kuwait. *International Journal of Modern Engineering Research (IJMER)*, 1403-1409.
5. Anin, E. K., Annan, J., & Alexander, O. F. (2013). Assessing the Causes of Urban Transportation Challenges in
the Kumasi Metropolis of Ghana. *American Based Research Journal*, ISSN (2304-7151) Vol. 2, Issue 6.
7. Asiyanboa, R. A.; Akinpelu, A. A. (2012). The challenges of on-street parking in Nigerian Cities' transportation routes. *International Journal of Development and Sustainability*, 476-489.
8. Harriet, T., Poku, K., & Emmanuel, A. K. (2013). Assessment of Traffic Congestion and Its Effects on
Productivity in Urban Ghana. *International Journal of Business and Social Science: Vol. 4 No. 3*, 225-235.
10. Ilsley, M. L. (2013). *A First Study of the Relationship Between Percentage of Illiteracy and Death Rate in American Cities*. Forgotten Books 2013.
11. Bomel Limited (2004). *Safety Culture and Work-Related Road Accidents*. London: Queen's Printer and
12. Controller of Her Majesty's Stationery Office 2004.
13. Lowe, C., Whitfield, G., Sutton, L., & Hardin, J. (2011). *Road User Safety and Disadvantage, Road Safety*
14. *Research Report No. 123*. London: Queen's Printer and Controller of Her Majesty's Stationery Office, 2011.
15. Mahmud, K., Gope, K., & Chowdhury, S. M. (2012). Possible Causes & Solutions of Traffic Jam and Their

16. Manville, Michael; Shoup, Donald;. (December, 2005). Parking, People and Cities. *Journal of Urban Planning*
17. Sisiopiku, V. P. (n.d.). On-Street Parking on State Roads. Retrieved from <http://ite.org/traffic/documents/AB01H6301.pdf> on 23/11/2013 at 7: 30 am
18. Al-Kayiem, H. H., Sidik, M. F. B. M., & Munusammy, Y. R. (2010). Study on the thermal accumulation and distribution inside a parked car cabin. *American Journal of Applied Sciences*, 7(6), 784-789.
19. Basar, M., Musa, M., Faizal, M., & Razik, N. (2013). Alternative Way in Reducing Car Cabin Temperature Using Portable Car Cooling System (Car-Cool). *International Journal of Innovative Technology and Exploring Engineering*, 3(3), 140-143.
20. Hitge, G., & Vanderschuren, M. (2015). Comparison of travel time between private car and public transport in Cape Town. *Journal of the South African Institution of Civil Engineering*, 57(3), 35-43. doi:<http://dx.doi.org/10.17159/2309-8775/2015/V57N3A5>
21. Khan, M., Kawaguchi, K., Okui, K., & Ohba, H. (2004). H222 Temperature Mitigation of the Parked Automobile under Blazing Sun. Paper presented at the NATIONAL HEAT TRANSFER SYMPOSIUM OF JAPAN.
22. Lee, J. (2017). Vehicle registrations in Malaysia hit 28.2 million units. Paultan.org. Retrieved from <https://paultan.org/2017/10/03/vehicle-registrations-in-malaysia-hit-28-2-million-units/>
23. <https://goodcalculators.com/inside-car-temperature-calculator/>